

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

Articles for publication in the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) should observe the following guidelines and style.

Guidelines

- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) may accompany each article. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Contributions should be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses should be done.
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Pest survey data should be quantified. Give infection percentage, degree of severity, etc.

Style

- For measurements, use the International System. Avoid national units of measure (cavan, rai, etc.).
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha, 2 h/d.
- Express yield data in tonnes per hectare (t/ha). With small-scale studies, use grams per pot (g/pot) or g/row
- Express time, money, and common measures in number, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 min, \$2, 3 kg/ha, 2-wk intervals.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or higher numbers. For example: six parts, seven tractors, four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 in Thailand, and 12 in Indonesia.
- Write out numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were put in each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer.
- Place the name or denotation of chemicals or other measured materials near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha, not 60 kg/ha N; 200 kg seed/ha, not 200 kg/ha seed.
- Use common names — not trade names — for chemicals.
- The US\$ is the standard monetary unit in the IRRN. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- When using acronyms, spell each out at first mention and put the specific acronym in parentheses. After that, use the acronym throughout the paper. For example: The brown planthopper (BPH) is a well-known insect pest of rice. Three BPH biotypes have been observed in Asia.
- Abbreviate names of months to three letters: Jun, Apr, Sep.
- Define in the footnote or legend any nonstandard abbreviations or symbols used in a table or figure.
- Do not cite references or include a bibliography.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization OVERALL PROGRESS

BU79, a promising induced rice genotype

N. G. Hajra and S. G. Hajra, Regional Research Centre, Kunjaban, Tripura (West), and E.H. Mallick, Rice Research Station, Bankura 722101, India

BU79 is a small-grained, high yielding mutant induced from Pankaj by 12 h treatment with ethyl methane

sulphonate. It has significantly better tillering, longer panicles, and more fertile grains per panicle than Pankaj.

BU79 was evaluated in multilocation yield trials at Burdwan, Suri, and Rampurhat in West Bengal in 1981. It yielded significantly more than Pankaj and Mahsuri at all locations (see table). BU79 is a suitable substitute for Pankaj and similar long duration rices. *ℓ*

Yield performance of BU79 in multilocal yield trial.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)			
	Burdwan	Suri	Rampurhat	Mean
BU79	5.6	5.1	5.0	5.2
Pankaj	4.8	4.6	4.5	4.6
Mahsuri	4.3	4.0	4.1	4.1
CD (P = 0.05)	0.6	0.4	0.3	

Karna: a high-yielding semidwarf for Karnataka

B. S. Naidu, B. Vidyachandra, M. G. Rao, and T. G. Reddy, Regional Research Station (RRS), V.C. Farm, Mandya, India

KMP39 (IET7209) has been released as Karna for southern Karnataka, India. It was developed at RRS, Mandya, from the F₂ of Jaya/ W 1263 that was received through the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project.

Karna is a semidwarf and matures in 130-135 d. Plant type is similar to, but slightly taller than, that of Jaya. Karna has compact tillering, medium panicles, erect flag leaves, and late senescence.

Spikelets are straw colored and awnless. The stigma is colorless and anthers are yellow. Kernels are 6.38 mm by 2.39 mm, with length-to-breadth ratio of 2.67. Grains are medium-slender and translucent and cook flaky with moderate volume expansion.

In 55 All India National Screening Nursery trials in 1979, Karna [tested as

Table 1. BI scores for Karna at Ponnampet, Karnataka, India.

Year	Variety	BI score	
		Leaf BI	Neck BI
1980	Karna	1.0	2.3
	Intan	3.0	5.0
1981	Karna	2.0	3.0
	Intan	3.0	6.0
1982	Karna	2.0	—
	Intan	9.0	—
Av	Karna	1.6	2.6
	Intan	5.0	5.5

Table 2. Karna grain yield in varietal yield trials in Karnataka in 1979-84.

Year	Yield (t/ha)	
	Karna	IR20
1979	4.6	4.1
1980	4.1	3.9
1981	5.9	4.9
1982	4.5	4.3
1983	4.7	4.2
1984	5.2	4.5
Av	4.8	4.2